

pale yellow solid (Ia) is formed (4 g), crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 122° (Found : C,54.18 ; H,5.13 ; N,6.97 ; S,9.29. $C_{28}H_{31}O_9N_3S_2$ requires : C,54.45 ; H,5.02 ; N, 6.80 ; S, 10.37%).

The other 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1, 5-diaryl-2, 4-isodithiobiurets are prepared by the interaction of phenylisothiocyanate and corresponding 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (Table 1).

II. *Preparation of 2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diaryl-2-isothiobiurets (II)* : Details of a typical experiment (where aryl=phenyl) are as follows : The phenyl isocyanate (0.01M, 1.3 ml) is added to a benzene solution of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide (0.01M, 4.82g in 30 ml). The mixture is kept at room temperature for 24 hrs. On mixing with petroleum ether it affords a granular solid (4 g), crystallized from ethanol, m. p. 159° (Found : C,55.72 ; H,4.95 ; N,6.51 ; S,5.67. $C_{28}H_{31}O_{10}N_3S$ requires : C,55.90 ; H,5.16 ; N,6.98 ; S,5.32%).

The other-2-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,5-diaryl-2-isothiobiurets are prepared by the interaction of phenyl isocyanate and related S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (Table 2).

The $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ of all the products are recorded in chloroform on Bellingham Polarimeter using sodium D-line. The uv spectra are recorded on Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer and the samples are prepared in chloroform. The ir spectra are recorded on Carl-Zeiss, Specord-75, spectrophotometer and the samples are prepared in Nujol as mull.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (I. D. B.) is grateful to U. G. C. for a teacher fellowship and to Dr. K.N. Munshi, Head of the Dept. of Chemistry, Nagpur University, for necessary facilities. Authors are also thankful to Prof. M. V. Kaulgud for help in recording specific rotation

References

1. I. GOODMAN, "Advances in Carbohydrate Chemistry", Ed. M. L. Wolfrom, Vol 13, Academic Press, New York, 1958.
2. (Miss) I. D. BEDEKAR and M. G. PARANJPE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 1014.
3. ARNOLD WEISSBERGER, "Physical methods of organic chemistry", Part II, 2nd Ed., Interscience Publisher, Inc., New York, 1949.
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of organic compounds", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1963.
5. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLEY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1964.

Synthesis of Thiazolo-thienopyrimidines

H. K. GAKHAR, (Miss) SUJATA BHARADWAJ, (Miss) ANJU JAIN and (Miss) P. BAVEJA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 10 November 1980, revised 17 June 1981, accepted 11 August 1981

SYNTHESIS of novel heterocyclics from 2-amino-3-carbomethoxy-4,5-dimethylthiophene (I) was reported by us in previous publications^{1,2}. We report now the synthesis of some thiazolo [3, 2-a] thieno [3, 2-e] pyrimidines from it.

Condensation of I with α -thiocyanoacetophenone (IIa) furnished 2,3-dimethyl-8-phenyl-4H-thiazolo [3,2-a] thieno [3, 2-e] pyrimidine-4-one (IIIa), the reaction having taken place as shown in the Chart I given below. The other derivatives of α -thiocyanoacetophenone (IIb-e) similarly condensed with I to give III b-e respectively.

Chart I

a, Ar = C_6H_5 ; b, Ar = $p\text{-Cl.C}_6H_4^-$; c, Ar = $p\text{-Br.C}_6H_4^-$; d, Ar = $p\text{-CH}_3.C_6H_4^-$; e, Ar = $p\text{-CH}_3O.C_6H_4^-$

PMR* spectrum of IIIa which gave signals at 2.48 (3H, s, CH_3 at C-3), 2.66(3H, s, CH_3 at C-2), 7.3-7.8 (6H, m, C_6H_5 and vinyl proton) confirms the structure but does not rule out the possibility for the compound to have linear structure VI. The isomeric compound VI was therefore synthesised in an unambiguous way. It was found to be a compound different from III as shown by m.p., tlc, etc. The compound VI was synthesised by condensing I with 2-chloro-4-phenylthiazole (IV) the reaction taking place as shown in Chart II below.

Chart II

The compound III and VI were reported earlier by Sauter *et al*³ who obtained them by treating 5, 6-dime-

*Chemical shifts given in this paper are in δ (ppm.)

TABLE 1—THIAZOLO [3,2-a] THIENO [3,2-e] PYRIMIDIN 4-ONES (III)

Compound	Thiocyanoketone used	Ar	Yield %	m. p. °C	M. F.	Analytical results	
						Found %	Required %
a	α -Thiocyano acetophenone	H	68	338	$C_{16}H_{12}N_2OS_2$	C, 62.01 H, 3.93 N, 9.40	61.54 3.85 8.98
b	<i>p</i> -Chloro α -thiocyano acetophenone	Cl	52	> 300	$C_{16}H_{11}ClN_2OS_2$	C, 55.73 H, 3.42 N, 8.12	55.41 3.17 8.08
c	<i>p</i> -Bromo α -thiocyano acetophenone	Br	53	> 300	$C_{16}H_{11}BrN_2OS_2$	C, 49.43 H, 3.08 N, 7.34	49.11 2.82 7.16
d	<i>p</i> -Methyl α -thiocyano acetophenone	CH ₃	63	> 300	$C_{17}H_{14}N_2OS_2$	N, 8.62	8.59
e	<i>p</i> -Methoxy α -thioeyano acetophenone	OCH ₃	56	> 300	$C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_2S_2$	C, 60.00 H, 4.12 N, 8.61	59.65 4.09 8.19

Compounds a, c, d and e were crystallised from ethanol and compound b was crystallised from dioxan.

thyl 2-phenacylthiothieno [2, 3-d] pyrimidine-4(3H)-one with sulphuric acid and arbitrarily assigned one the structure IIIa (m.p. 336-8°) and the other VI (m.p. 228-30°). The present work incidentally shows the assignment to be correct.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in paraffin liquid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken on Perkin Elmer grating IR spectrometer 621 in nujol and pmr was recorded on 60 MHz Varian spectrometer in TFA.

2,3-Dimethyl-8-aryl-4H-thiazolo [3, 2-a] thieno [3, 2-e] pyrimidine-4-one(III a-e) :

A solution of α -thiocyanoacetophenone(II, 0.01 mole) in ethanol (10 ml) was mixed with an ethanolic solution of 2-amino-3-carbethoxy-4,5-dimethylthiophene hydrochloride (I, 2.35 g; 0.01 mole in 20 ml) and refluxed on a steam bath for 7 hrs. The solid that separated on cooling was collected and crystallised from ethanol. Additional amount of the compound was obtained by concentrating the mother liquor Table 1.

Ethyl 2-[(4-phenylthiazolyl) amino]-4, 5-dimethyl-3-thiophenecarboxylate (V) :

A mixture of I (1.99 g; 0.01 mole) and 2-chloro-4-phenylthiazole (IV, 1.95 g; 0.01 mole) was heated on a steam bath for 2 hrs. The hard mass formed was triturated with ethanol (3 ml) and basified with aq. sodium carbonate (10%). The product that separated was crystallised from ethanol as brown needles m.p. 138°, yield 1.97 g (55%). Found : N, 7.64; $C_{18}H_{18}N_2O_2S_2$ requires N, 7.82%.

6, 7-Dimethyl-3-phenyl-5H-thiazolo [3, 2-a] thieno [2, 3-d] pyrimidine-5-one (VI) :

Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through an ethanolic solution of V (1.1 g; 0.003 mole in 15 ml). It was refluxed for 4 hrs. Ethanol was removed by distillation and the residue was treated with aq. sodium carbonate (5%). The product which separated was crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles m.p. 230°; yield 0.8 g (83%). Found : C, 61.66; H, 3.80; $C_{18}H_{18}N_2OS_2$ requires C, 61.54; H, 3.85%.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor O. P. Vig, Chairman, Chemistry Department, Panjab University for the laboratory facilities, to Messrs B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar of this Department for analysis and to Professor V. K. Ahluwalia, Chemistry Department, Delhi University, for the pmr spectrum of the compound. One of them (A.J.) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. H. K. GAKHAR, SUJATA BHARADWAJ and (Mrs.) P. BAVEJA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15B, 347.
2. H. K. GAKHAR, ANIL KHANNA and (Mrs.) P. BAVEJA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16B 305.
3. F. SAUTER, W. DIENHAMMER and P. STANETTY, *Mh. Chem.*, 1974, 105, 1258.

Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of N-(substituted Benzylidene)-*p*-(2-Benzimidazolyl)phenoxyacetyl Hydrazides

SURENDRA BAHADUR, (Miss) MUKTA SAXENA and KRISHNA K. PANDEY

Chemistry Department, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 19 December 1980, revised 6 June 1981, accepted 11 August 1981

BENZIMIDAZOLES have been associated with antiviral¹, antifungal², antibacterial³, insecticidal⁴ and other biological properties⁵. A large number of hydrazides and hydrazones have been reported to possess bactericidal properties⁶⁻⁸. Keeping these observation in mind, a new ester, its hydrazide and hydrazones all containing a benzimidazole moiety have been synthesised to study if the products could display any biological properties.

2-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl) benzimidazole (Scheme I) was prepared according to reported method^{9,10}. Ethyl-*p*-(2-benzimidazolyl)phenoxy acetate (II) was synthesised by the reaction of I and ethylchloroacetate. Hydrolysis of the ester(II) in absolute alcohol gave *p*-(2-